

Interest and Psychological Well- Being of School Teachers: A Correlational Study

Chiya Jaiswal and O. P. Sharma

University of Rajasthan, Jaipur

Teaching is one of the noble professions in the world. A teacher shapes the future of the nation. It is very important to focus on the Psychological Well- Being of the teachers. The study aims at understanding the relationship between Interest in teaching profession and the Psychological Well- Being of the teachers working in private schools. For the present study, 60 teachers of age range 25 to 35 were selected from rural areas using purposive sampling method. The sample was sub-divided into categories of male and female to assess the relationship of interest with psychological well-being. Point Biserial correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the correlation. The r value obtained was 0.97635 which is significant at 0.01 levels. The 60 teachers were classified into low and high interest in teaching profession group with 30 subjects in each group. The df was 58 and the obtained t - value was 34.3950 which indicate a p value less than 0.0001 which is significant at 0.01 levels. When the subjects were divided in terms of their gender, the obtained value of t test was 0.4118 and the p - value obtained was 0.682004 which is not significant at 0.01 levels which indicates that no significant difference lies between male and female groups in the levels of Psychological well-being.

Keywords: Teaching, Interest, Psychological Well- Being

The statement, "The destiny of India is being shaped in the classroom," from the Kothari Commission (1964-1966), underscores the critical role that education plays in the development and progress of a nation. The statement acknowledges that the quality of education directly impacts a country's destiny. Education is seen as a fundamental factor in determining a nation's level of prosperity and the well-being of its people. A well-educated population is more likely to contribute to economic growth and individual prosperity. Education is also linked to national security. A well-educated populace is better equipped to understand and address the challenges and threats that a nation might face. Education can contribute to social cohesion and stability.

The National Policy on Education (1986) underscores the importance of establishing

a National System of Education that is designed to preserve the country's unique socio-cultural identity while addressing contemporary challenges and promoting educational equality. This national system is envisioned as a common educational structure that spans the entire country, with a national curriculum framework containing core components of national significance. It recognizes education as a cornerstone of a nation's progress and development.

Interest

Interest is indeed a crucial variable that significantly influences the teaching and learning process. When individuals engage in tasks or activities that they have a genuine interest in, they are more likely to excel and be fully committed to the task at hand. Conversely, attempting to carry out a task

without interest can result in a lackluster and incomplete outcome.

The term “interest” has its origins in the Latin word “intersee,” which conveys the idea of making a difference or mattering. Interest, in this context, refers to an innate or acquired feeling that motivates us to engage in spontaneous activities. It is a vital factor in sustaining our consistent and persistent behavior. In essence, interests are rooted in our natural instincts or tendencies. Interest helps us select and prioritize specific activities, which is closely related to the process of attention.

In the context of education, interest plays a vital role. It can be described as the inclination or desire to engage with a particular subject matter, activity, or person. It essentially explains why individuals tend to gravitate toward certain situations and why they react to them selectively.

As Kulshethra (1984) defines it, interest is the innate tendency to consistently make choices in a specific direction, even in the absence of external pressure or when presented with alternatives. It serves as a motivating force that drives an individual to wholeheartedly immerse themselves in a particular task or endeavor.

According to Kelley, an individual’s interests can reveal important information about their personality. The types of activities or subjects that someone finds interesting can be indicative of their values, preferences, and characteristics.

W.V. Bingham’s definition of interest further emphasizes the concept. Bingham describes interest as a tendency within individuals to become absorbed in a particular experience and to continue engaging with it. This definition highlights the immersive and enduring nature of interest. When someone is genuinely interested in something, they tend to become deeply

engrossed in it, which can lead to sustained involvement and a desire to explore it further.

In summary, interest is not just a matter of personal preference; it also offers valuable insights into an individual’s personality and their propensity to become absorbed in and continue engaging with particular experiences or activities.

Teaching and Interest

Teachers hold a critical and influential role in the educational system, shaping the lives of students and contributing significantly to the learning process. While possessing knowledge of the subject matter and professionalism are crucial aspects of being a good teacher, one of the most vital factors is the teacher’s interest in teaching.

Interest serves as the driving force behind the entire process of teaching and learning. All efforts in education are directed toward fostering students’ interest in learning. If teachers lack interest in their work, it can have detrimental effects on students’ lives and learning experiences.

Interest in teaching can be defined as the enthusiasm or liking for the activities related to teaching and learning that are chosen by student teachers. It reflects the teacher’s passion and commitment to their role in educating students.

The Holland interest codes

John Holland’s theory of vocational interests explained 6 types of interests, known as RIASEC types. These six types represent different vocational interests. These codes help people understand their vocational preferences and align them with suitable career paths. Here’s a brief explanation of each of the six types:

- **Realistic (R):** Realistic individuals have an interest in working with tools, machines, or physical objects. They often prefer practical, hands-on

activities and enjoy solving concrete problems. Careers in trades, engineering, construction, or agriculture may align with their interests.

- **Investigative (I):** Investigative individuals are curious and analytical. They enjoy solving complex problems, conducting research, and thinking deeply about various subjects. Careers in science, research, technology, or academia may appeal to them.
- **Artistic (A):** Artistic individuals are creative and imaginative. They have a strong interest in creative and novel activities, including visual and performing arts, writing, and design. Careers in the arts, entertainment, media, or design fields often attract them.
- **Social (S):** As you mentioned, social individuals have interests in social activities like teaching, helping others, and building relationships. They are often empathetic, and they thrive in roles that involve interaction, counseling, education, or healthcare.
- **Enterprising (E):** Enterprising individuals are persuasive and enjoy leading and influencing others. They are often goal-oriented and thrive in roles that involve sales, management, entrepreneurship, or leadership.
- **Conventional (C):** Conventional individuals prefer systematic and organized activities. They like working with data, details, and procedures. Careers in finance, administration, data analysis, and quality control often align with their interests.

Holland's theory suggests that individuals seek occupations that align with their vocational interests, leading to greater job

satisfaction and performance. When a person's interests match the interests associated with a job or work environment, it's referred to as congruence.

Psychological Well-Being

The World Health Organization's definition of health from 50 years ago emphasized a holistic view of health. It stated that health is not just the absence of disease or infirmity but a state of complete well-being, which includes physical, mental, and social dimensions. This definition highlights the importance of considering not only physical health but also mental and social well-being when assessing an individual's or a population's health. It has had a significant impact on how health and healthcare are understood and addressed worldwide. Well-being is a complex construct studied within positive mental health. Two main approaches are identified: subjective well-being and psychological well-being.

Subjective well-being is often assessed using hedonic measures and it primarily focuses on an individual's overall sense of happiness, life satisfaction, and the experience of positive emotions. It is essentially a person's subjective assessment of their own well-being.

Psychological well-being, on the other hand, is measured using eudemonic measures and emphasizes deeper aspects of well-being, such as meaning, optimal functioning, and self-actualization. This approach suggests that well-being is achieved by aligning one's actions and feelings with their true self or personal values. Carol Ryff's model of psychological well-being, which includes dimensions like self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and personal growth, provides a framework for understanding and assessing these deeper aspects of well-being. It draws inspiration from various psychological

theories and encompasses six dimensions, each contributing to overall well-being:

A clear summary of the dimensions of psychological well-being according to Carol Ryff's model can be:

- **Self-Acceptance:** This dimension represents the core of mental health and encompasses self-actualization, optimal functioning, and maturity. It reflects how individuals accept and value themselves.
- **Positive Relations with Others:** This dimension involves the ability to build close and trust-based interpersonal relationships. It also reflects an individual's capacity to experience and express love towards others.
- **Autonomy:** Autonomy relates to self-determination, independence, and the ability to regulate one's behavior from within. It indicates a person's capacity to make choices and decisions based on their own values and beliefs.
- **Environmental Mastery:** This dimension pertains to an individual's ability to engage in both physical and mental activities that lead to personal growth. It also involves the capacity to adapt to and creatively influence the external world.
- **Purpose in Life:** Having a sense of purpose is essential for psychological well-being. This dimension reflects the presence of clear intentions, goals, and a sense of direction in one's life.
- **Personal Growth:** Personal growth represents the ongoing development and expansion of an individual's capacity to grow and evolve throughout their life. It encompasses the idea that individuals can continue to learn, change, and develop over time.

These dimensions together contribute to an individual's overall psychological well-being, reflecting the deeper aspects of their mental health and life satisfaction.

Objectives

- To understand the relationship between interest in teaching profession and Psychological well-being of teachers.
- To understand the relationship between interest in teaching profession and Psychological well-being of teachers on the basis of sex (Male and Female).

Hypotheses

- There would be a positive relationship between interest in teaching profession and Psychological well-being of teachers.
- There would be no significant difference between interest in teaching profession and Psychological well-being of teachers on the basis of sex (Male and Female).

Method

Sample

60 teachers working in private schools were selected for the present study using purposive sampling. 30 males and 30 females teachers were selected working in rural areas.

Inclusion Criteria: Both males and females teachers working in private schools in rural areas (age range 25 to 35), were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: The study excluded physically handicapped and psychologically disordered teachers, with an age range restriction from below 25 to above 35 years. It also excluded teachers from government schools, concentrating on those from private

or non-government schools or schools of non-rural areas. These exclusions were made to define a specific group of teachers for the study, aligning with the research objectives.

Psychological Measures

The Self-Directed Search (SDS; Holland, Fritzsche, & Powell, 1994) : It is an interest inventory that categorizes an individual's interests based on Holland's RIASEC theory. This theory classifies interests into six main categories: Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional. The SDS helps individuals explore their career options by matching their interests with occupational themes associated with these categories. It is a valuable tool for career development and vocational guidance. Its cronbach's alpha coefficients > .90 for all six codes and average variance extracted > .50 indicate convergent validity.

Psychological Well-being Scale (Carol D. Ryff, 2007): Carol Ryff developed the Psychological well-being scale (Revised Form) for measuring psychological wellbeing. The scale contains 42 items with six- point rating options. It covers six dimensions of psychological wellbeing. The six dimensions it covers are Autonomy, Environmental mastery, Personal Growth, Positive relations with others, Purpose in life and Self-acceptance. The test- retest reliability is > .80 for all the six dimensions.

Procedure The study was conducted whereby the subjects were listed on the basis of criteria inclusion and exclusion of the study. After obtaining consent from the subjects, the psychological measures of the study were sent via Google Forms.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

In trying to study the actual study hypothesis, overall descriptive statistics like Mean and Standard Deviation were

calculated. Table I shows the descriptive analysis, i.e., mean and standard deviation scores for psychological well-being among male and female subjects. The Mean score of males is 178.1 which is more than that of females' mean score which is 174.1 for Psychological well-being. The Standard deviations for males and females are 38.69 and 36.52 respectively for Psychological well-being. Both mean and SD values are more for males than females. The data of the variable of interest in teaching profession was in nominal scale and hence is coded as 0 for low interest and 1 for high interest. The mean and SD for interest in teaching profession is 0 and 1 respectively for both males and females. Overall the mean score of Psychological well-being for low interest in teaching is 139.93 for low interest in teaching is 212.27 respectively. The SD for low interest in teaching is 7.29 and for low interest in teaching are 8.92 respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis-Mean and Standard Deviation for Interest and Psychological Well-Being among Male and Female teachers

Variables	N	Gender	MEAN		SD	
Interest	30	Male	1		0	
	30	Female	1		0	
Psychological well-being	30	Male	178.1		38.69	
	30	Female	174.1		36.52	
Total	60	Interest	0	1	0	1
		PWB	139.93	212.27	7.29	8.92

Point Biserial Correlation Since the data obtained was in nominal and interval scale form, Point Biserial correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the correlation between Interest in teaching profession and Psychological Well-Being. The r value obtained was 0.97635 which is found significant at 0.01 levels which is an indicator of the existence of a positive relationship

between both the variables. As the Interest in teaching profession increases, Psychological well-being increases. Table II depicts the same.

Table 2: Point Biserial correlation between interest and PWB

Variable	r	p- value	Significance level
Interest and PWB	0.97635	<.00001	0.01

Significant difference among Variables by applying t-test: This section includes the results representing significant differences among the variables. There were 60 teachers, half of which had low and other halves had high interest in the profession of teaching. The degree of freedom is 58 and obtained t- value is 34.3950 which indicate a p value less than 0.0001 which is found significant at 0.01 levels. This indicates that there exists a significant difference between the low interest and high interest group in terms of their Psychological well-being.

When the subjects were divided in terms of their gender to assess whether there is any difference in Psychological well-being and interest on the basis of gender, 30 subjects were in each group. The df is 58 and the obtained t- value is 0.4118 for the 60 participants for Psychological well-being variable. The p- value obtained is 0.682004 which is not significant at 0.01 levels which indicates that insignificant difference lies between the male and female groups in terms of the levels of Psychological well-being. This implies that gender has no role in determining the Psychological well-being in terms of the interest of subjects in teaching profession.

Limitations and Ideas for Further Study

The research took place in the state of Rajasthan in India. So it is crucial to cover other regions as well to get a diverse picture. Also, there were 60 school teachers of secondary level in the present study. A larger

sample can be used. The sample belonged to the age range of 25 to 35. Further studies can involve teachers of more age groups and can compare them too. Subjects belonged to rural area and hence, teachers of urban areas can also be included and can be compared with rural subjects. Teachers in this study worked in private schools. Government school teachers can also be included in further researches. Teachers working in colleges and universities can also be included in the study. Along with Psychological well-being, subjective well-being can also be studied in future researches.

Table 3: Degree of freedom, t-scores, and significance level

Variable	df	t- value	p value	Significance level	Inter-pretation
Interest (low and high) and PWB	58	34.3950	<0.0001	0.01	Significant
Interest and PWB – male and female	58	0.4118	0.682004	0.01	Not significant

Conclusion

The point Biserial correlation coefficient indicates a positive relation between interest in teaching profession and psychological well-being of the teachers. There is a significant difference between low and high interest group in terms of their PWB. Also, there exists no significant difference between male and female groups in terms of their interest and PWB levels. Hence, the obtained results support our hypotheses.

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Chiya Jaiswal, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, (Raj.) 302004. studypsychologywithchiya@gmail.com

O. P. Sharma, Head & Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur (Raj.) 302004. opbrd65@gmail.com